

THE 3D PRESSURE-DEPENDENT ELASTO-PLASTIC CONSTITUTIVE MODEL WITHIN TENSION-COMPRESSION ASYMMETRY AND ITS APPLICATION TO PREDICT LAMINATES' RESPONSES UNDER OFF-AXIS LOADING CONDITIONS

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ABSTRACT

Nonlinear responses of fiber-reinforced composite laminates subjected to off-axis loading conditions was focused on and a novel elasto-plastic constitutive model was developed. The approach where the square root of the linear combination of the plastic potential function and the hydrostatic pressure term forms the effective stress was utilized to develop a new elasto-plastic constitutive model. The tension-compression asymmetry in laminates' yielding was incorporated in the plastic potential function. The non-associative flow rule was followed and the exponential hardening law was taken. Procedures of numerical implementation and determination of model parameters of the new elasto-plastic constitutive model were elaborated on. Three cases of off-axis loading test on unidirectional laminates made of different materials were simulated by FEM software based on the proposed model. Available experimental results proved the capabilities of the model in predicting composite laminates' nonlinear elasto-plastic responses. The difference between laminates' yielding behaviours under tension and compression were well captured by this constitutive model.

1 INTRODUCTION

Being one of the primary nonlinear behaviours of fiber-reinforced polymer matrix composite (PMC) laminates under various loading conditions, laminate plasticity has been focused on by researchers for proper mathematical characterization in finite element analysis (FEA), which is necessary for accurate FEA of laminate structures' responses and efficient design of light-weight PMC laminate structures holding certain stiffness and impact resistance.

Continuous efforts have been devoted into describing macroscopic plastic behaviours of PMC laminates. Chen and Sun [1] developed a one parameter elasto-plastic model based on the Hill-type yield function, where isotropic hardening law together with the associative flow rule were applied. Uniaxial loading test results were sufficient for describing laminate nonlinear plasticity in their model. Due to the simplicity and accuracy, Sun and Chen's one parameter elasto-plastic model has been extensively studied. Both the 2D form and 3D extensions of Sun and Chen's elasto-plastic model proved to well predict PMC laminate plastic responses in off-axis loading conditions [1-4]. Because of polymer material's pressure-dependent mechanical behaviours, the yielding process of PMC laminates were found sensitive to hydrostatic pressure [5, 6]. Considering pressure-dependent yielding behaviours of polymer based composites, Yokozeki, et al. [7] extended Sun's plasticity model into the two-parameter form and the hydrostatic pressure term [8] was incorporated into the stress potential. In both Yokozeki's model [7] and Sun's models [1, 3], the power function of the isotropic hardening law was applied, in case of which Ren [9] explained that the divided zero term is included when the effective plastic strain is zero. It is mathematically unacceptable and may incorrectly lead to zero incremental plastic multiplier and therefore the zero incremental plastic strain in the plastic yielding process. As a result, Yokozeki's model was modified and a new constitutive pressure-dependent plastic model within the non-associative flow rule and exponential hardening function was proposed

by Ren, et al.[10]. Off-axis loading test results were found to agree well with predicted laminate responses based on Ren's model.

Apart from the pressure dependence, tension-compression asymmetry of PMC laminates' yielding behaviours was observed in off-axis loading tests[7, 11-13]. Hoffman [14] and Tsai and Wu [15] attributed the tension and compression asymmetry to different yield strengths exhibited by composites in compression and tension and developed several anisotropic yield criteria. Kawai, et al. [16, 17] and Cazacu, et al. [18] introduced a parameter in the yielding function to capture the tension-compression asymmetry. Tham, et al. [11] took advantages of Cazacu's yielding function and demonstrated the significance of considering the tension-compression asymmetry in FEA of laminates bending responses. Based on the approach proposed by Kawai, et al. [16, 17] and the Hill yield function [19], Wang, et al. [13, 20] proposed a new elasto-plastic constitutive model, in which the linear combination of the hydrostatic pressure term and the positive square root of plastic potential was applied and the associative flow rule was followed. The pressure dependence and the tension-compression asymmetry of plastic yielding in PMC laminates were simultaneously accomplished in Wang's model. And the predicted laminates' elasto-plastic behaviours in off-axis tension and compression based on Wang's model proved to agree well with off-axis test results.

However, limitations do exist in Wang's plasticity model. The effect of stress along fiber direction on laminate plasticity confirmed by Frans [21] and Mena-Tun, et al. [22] was not contained in Wang's model where only the transverse stress and shear stress terms were found. Meanwhile, the developed Wang's model mainly focused on plane stress conditions [13, 20] and was insufficient to accurately predict laminate nonlinear behaviours under multiaxial loading conditions. In order to incorporate the influence of hydrostatic pressure on the constitutive behaviour of the fiber-reinforced plastics, it is necessary to account for the fully three-dimensional stress state in laminates. What's more, in contrast to the associative flow rule, the non-associative flow rule allows the accurate prediction of the plastic Poisson coefficients and of the volumetric plastic strains for pressure sensitive materials [6, 23]. When the non-associative flow rule is utilized in Wang's model [13, 20, 24, 25], the linear combination form of the hydrostatic pressure term and the positive square root of plastic potential would lead to a complicated form of incremental plastic strain. Then, the numerical implementation tends to be more complex than that in the associative flow rule.

According to limitations existing in above-mentioned elasto-plastic models, a new three-dimensional elasto-plastic constitutive model based on Wang's model is developed in this paper. Via a newly formulated plastic potential function based on the Hill yield criterion, the tension-compression asymmetry, the effect of stress term along fiber direction and the hydrostatic pressure term on plastic yielding are incorporated into the elasto-plastic model. In this paper, the literature of constitutive modeling of laminate plasticity and the research focus are states in section 1. Section 2 gives details about the newly constructed elasto-plastic model and the corresponding numerical implementation procedures is listed in section 3. Three cases of off-axis loading tests on different laminates are simulated based on the built model in section 4. Section 5 made comparisons and discussions for validating the developed model. Conclusions are drawn in Section 6.

2 THE ELASTO-PLASTIC CONSTITUTIVE MODEL

2.1 Constitutive modeling of laminate anisotropic plasticity

Unidirectional fiber-reinforced PMC laminates' nonlinear responses under loading circumstances within the scope of low strain rate are mainly focused on and the infinitesimal deformation is assumed in this paper. The whole strain tensor $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$ is decomposed into the elastic strain tensor $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^e$ and the plastic strain tensor $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^p$, where the bold symbols are used to represent tensorial characters.

Unidirectional composite laminates are composed of stacks of laminas and each composite lamina is assumed to be homogeneously orthotropic. The principal material axis includes 1-2-3 where the axis 1, 2, 3 respectively aligns along the fiber direction, the transverse direction in the lamina's plane and the thickness direction through the lamina. The relationship between stress and strain in each lamina is

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma} = \mathbf{C} : \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^e = \mathbf{C} : (\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} - \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^p) \quad (1)$$

in which $\boldsymbol{\sigma} = [\sigma_{11} \ \sigma_{22} \ \sigma_{33} \ \sigma_{12} \ \sigma_{23} \ \sigma_{13}]^T$, $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} = [\varepsilon_{11} \ \varepsilon_{22} \ \varepsilon_{33} \ \varepsilon_{12} \ \varepsilon_{23} \ \varepsilon_{13}]^T$ and \mathbf{C} represents the orthotropic stiffness matrix.

Herein, a new formulation of effective stress σ_{eff} is introduced in Eq (2) for considering the tension and compression yielding asymmetry as well as the effect of hydrostatic pressure on yielding.

$$\sigma_{\text{eff}} = \sqrt{\frac{3}{2} \left[(\sigma_{22} - \sigma_{33})^2 + 2\Gamma a_{66} (\sigma_{12}^2 + \sigma_{13}^2) + 2a_{44} \sigma_{23}^2 \right] + a_{11} (\sigma_{11} + \sigma_{22} + \sigma_{33})^2 + (\Gamma - 1) (\sigma_{22} + \sigma_{33})^2 \text{sig}(\sigma_{22} + \sigma_{33})} \quad (2)$$

in which the parameter a_{66}, a_{44} respectively denotes the contribution of the in-plane shear stress and transverse shear stress to yielding behaviors. The parameter a_{11} quantifies the influence of hydrostatic pressure term on material's yielding behavior. $\text{sig}(x)$ denotes a nonlinear function in which $\text{sig}(x)$ equals to 1 when x is greater than zero and $\text{sig}(x)$ holds -1 when x is less than zero and otherwise $\text{sig}(x)$ becomes zero. Similar to Wang's manipulation [13, 20], the parameter Γ is utilized to represent the differences between the yielding behaviors under tension and compression conditions.

Meanwhile, the plastic potential function is

$$g = \frac{1}{2} \left[(\sigma_{22} - \sigma_{33})^2 + 2\Gamma a_{66} (\sigma_{12}^2 + \sigma_{13}^2) + 2a_{44} \sigma_{23}^2 \right] + \frac{1}{3} a_{11} (\sigma_{11} + \sigma_{22} + \sigma_{33})^2 + \frac{1}{3} (\Gamma - 1) (\sigma_{22} + \sigma_{33})^2 \text{sig}(\sigma_{22} + \sigma_{33}) \quad (3)$$

Following the non-associative flow rule, the incremental plastic strain $d\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^p$ could be obtained as

$$d\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^p = d\lambda^p \cdot \frac{\partial g}{\partial \boldsymbol{\sigma}} \quad (4)$$

in which $d\lambda^p$ denotes the incremental plastic multiplier and the detailed components in the incremental plastic strain tensor refers to Eq (5).

$$d\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^p = \begin{bmatrix} d\varepsilon_{11}^p \\ d\varepsilon_{22}^p \\ d\varepsilon_{33}^p \\ d\varepsilon_{12}^p \\ d\varepsilon_{23}^p \\ d\varepsilon_{13}^p \end{bmatrix} = \frac{2}{3} d\lambda^p \cdot \begin{bmatrix} a_{11} (\sigma_{11} + \sigma_{22} + \sigma_{33}) \\ \frac{3}{2} (\sigma_{22} - \sigma_{33}) + a_{11} (\sigma_{11} + \sigma_{22} + \sigma_{33}) + (\Gamma - 1) (\sigma_{22} + \sigma_{33}) \text{sig}(\sigma_{22} + \sigma_{33}) \\ -\frac{3}{2} (\sigma_{22} - \sigma_{33}) + a_{11} (\sigma_{11} + \sigma_{22} + \sigma_{33}) + (\Gamma - 1) (\sigma_{22} + \sigma_{33}) \text{sig}(\sigma_{22} + \sigma_{33}) \\ 3\Gamma a_{66} \sigma_{12} \\ 3\Gamma a_{44} \sigma_{23} \\ 3\Gamma a_{66} \sigma_{13} \end{bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

In the non-associative flow scheme, the new formulation of plastic potential results in a more concise form of mathematical representations of incremental plastic strains than those based on models using the linear combination of the hydrostatic pressure term and the positive square root of the plastic potential function [13, 16, 17, 20, 24, 25]. The certification is similar to that in Appendix A attached to Ref [10] and is not specifically explained here.

The isotropic strain hardening behavior is taken into account in the elasto-plastic model. The power law function were commonly utilized to represent the relationship between effective stress and effective plastic strain. Whereas the divided zero term is included when the effective plastic strain is zero, which is mathematically unacceptable [9]. Consequently, the exponential function is adopted. The isotropic hardening function R differs respective under tension and compression status and is determined by effective plastic strain $\varepsilon_{\text{eff}}^p$.

$$R(\varepsilon_{\text{eff}}^{\text{p}}) = \begin{cases} R_{0T} + A_{1T} \cdot e^{-\frac{\varepsilon_{\text{eff}}^{\text{p}}}{B_{1T}}} + A_{2T} \cdot e^{-\frac{\varepsilon_{\text{eff}}^{\text{p}}}{B_{2T}}} + A_{3T} \cdot e^{-\frac{\varepsilon_{\text{eff}}^{\text{p}}}{B_{3T}}}; & \sigma_{22} + \sigma_{33} > 0 \\ R_{0C} + A_{1C} \cdot e^{-\frac{\varepsilon_{\text{eff}}^{\text{p}}}{B_{1C}}} + A_{2C} \cdot e^{-\frac{\varepsilon_{\text{eff}}^{\text{p}}}{B_{2C}}} + A_{3C} \cdot e^{-\frac{\varepsilon_{\text{eff}}^{\text{p}}}{B_{3C}}}; & \sigma_{22} + \sigma_{33} \leq 0 \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

in which $R_{0i}, A_{1i}, B_{1i}, A_{2i}, B_{2i}, A_{3i}, B_{3i} (i = T, C)$ are material constants and could be obtained by curve fitting of the effective stress-effective strain curve.

The following yield function combines the effective stress in Eq (2) and the isotropic strain hardening function in Eq (6) together and it is explained by Eq (7).

$$F(\boldsymbol{\sigma}, \varepsilon_{\text{eff}}^{\text{p}}) = \sigma_{\text{eff}} - R(\varepsilon_{\text{eff}}^{\text{p}}) \quad (7)$$

According to the incremental plastic work dW^{p} in the unit material cell and $dW^{\text{p}} = \boldsymbol{\sigma} \cdot d\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{\text{p}} = \sigma_{\text{eq}} \cdot d\varepsilon_{\text{eq}}^{\text{p}}$, the relationship between the incremental effective plastic strain and the incremental plastic multiplier based can be acquired.

$$d\varepsilon_{\text{eff}}^{\text{p}} = \frac{2}{3} \sigma_{\text{eff}} d\lambda^{\text{p}} \quad (8)$$

During the yielding process, the following Kuhn-tucker loading condition should be satisfied[26] and then material stress and strain could be obtained via numerical iterations.

$$F \leq 0; \dot{\lambda}^{\text{p}} \geq 0; F \dot{\lambda}^{\text{p}} = 0; \dot{F} = 0. \quad (9)$$

2.2 Determination procedures of model parameters

All material parameters including $a_{11}, a_{44}, a_{66}, \Gamma$ and $R_{0i}, A_{1i}, B_{1i}, A_{2i}, B_{2i}, A_{3i}, B_{3i} (i = T, C)$ could be acquired from off-axis tension and compression test results. The approach is based on selecting proper values of above parameters to enable all off-axis tested effective stress-effective plastic strain curves collapse into one master curve respective in tension and compression conditions, which is elaborated on in Ref [1, 4, 10]. The determination process is briefly introduced here.

In off-axis loading tests, the local rectangular coordinate (1–2–3) where 1-direction coincides with material principal direction and the global rectangular coordinate (x-y-z) where x coincides with the loading direction are defined. Plane (x-y) and plane (1–2) are in the uniaxial loading plane, and the 3 direction coincides with z axis. The off-axis loading angle is θ . Then stresses in material principal directions can be expressed by applied stress and the strain term along loading direction could also be obtained [7, 10].

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_{11} &= \sigma_x \cos^2 \theta \\ \sigma_{22} &= \sigma_x \sin^2 \theta \\ \sigma_{12} &= -\sigma_x \sin \theta \cos \theta \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

$$d\varepsilon_x^{\text{p}} = d\varepsilon_{11}^{\text{p}} \cos^2 \theta + d\varepsilon_{22}^{\text{p}} \sin^2 \theta - 2d\varepsilon_{12}^{\text{p}} \sin \theta \cos \theta \quad (11)$$

With manipulations of Eq (2-5) and Eq (8, 10, 11), the effective stress σ_{eff} and effective plastic strain $\varepsilon_{\text{eff}}^{\text{p}}$ under the uniaxial loading can be derived as follows.

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_{\text{eff}} &= h(\theta) \cdot |\sigma_x| \\ \varepsilon_{\text{eff}}^{\text{p}} &= \frac{|\sigma_x|}{h(\theta) \cdot \sigma_x} \cdot \left(\varepsilon_x - \frac{\sigma_x}{E_x} \right) \\ h(\theta) &= \sqrt{\frac{3}{2} \sin^4 \theta + 3\Gamma a_{66} \sin^2 \theta \cos^2 \theta + a_{11} + (\Gamma - 1) \sin^4 \theta \cdot \text{sig}(\sigma_x)} \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

where E_x is the young's modulus along the loading direction and can be derived from the initial elastic slope of stress-strain curves in off-axis loading tests. $a_{44} = 2.0$ commonly suggested by researchers [1, 4, 27] was taken in this paper. Then, the values of a_{11}, a_{66}, Γ can be selected by trial and error until all of the effective stress- effective strain curves of the off-axis loading tests collapse into one single master curve respectively in tension and compression conditions. Once the effective stress-effective strain curves in tension and compression are obtained, the exponential hardening function Eq (4) is used to fit the parameters $R_{0i}, A_{1i}, B_{1i}, A_{2i}, B_{2i}, A_{3i}, B_{3i}$ ($i = T, C$). Parameters contains subscript "T" and "C" are respectively fitted from the effective stress-strain curve in tension tests and that in compression tests.

2.3 Numerical implementation procedures

The incremental elasto-plastic constitutive model consists of the elastic stress-strain relationship in Eq (1), the non-associative flow rule in Eq (4), the isotropic hardening law in Eq (6), the yield criterion in Eq (7) and the Kuhn-Tucker loading/unloading conditions in Eq (9). The discretized strain-driven incremental elasto-plastic model based on the implicit backward Euler scheme is in the form of following set of equations:

$$\begin{aligned}\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{n+1} &= \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_n + \Delta \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{n+1}, \\ \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{n+1}^p &= \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_n^p + \Delta \lambda_{n+1}^p \cdot \partial_{\boldsymbol{\sigma}} \boldsymbol{g}_{n+1}, \\ \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{\text{eff},n+1}^p &= \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{\text{eff},n}^p + \frac{2}{3} \boldsymbol{\sigma}_{\text{eff},n+1} \cdot \Delta \lambda_{n+1}^p, \\ \boldsymbol{\sigma}_{n+1} &= \boldsymbol{\sigma}_n + \boldsymbol{C} : (\Delta \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{n+1} - \Delta \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{n+1}^p), \\ F\left(\boldsymbol{\sigma}_{n+1}(\Delta \lambda_{n+1}^p), \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{\text{eff},n+1}^p(\Delta \lambda_{n+1}^p)\right) &\leq 0.\end{aligned}$$

where $\Delta \lambda_{n+1}^p$ denotes the plastic multiplier in the (n+1)th increment. The process acquiring the plastic deformation is based on the closest point projection return mapping algorithm and the numerical procedures are elaborated on as follows:

a. Initialization of the (n+1)th increment

Read the current incremental strain $\Delta \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{n+1}$, the current time increment Δt_{n+1} and the state variables in the previous increment $\boldsymbol{\sigma}_n, \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_n, \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_n^e, \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_n^p, \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{\text{eff},n}^p$.

b. Update the trial stress and strain

Assume that no plastic deformation happens $\Delta \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{n+1}^{\text{p,trial}} = \mathbf{0}, \Delta \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{\text{eff},n+1}^{\text{p,trial}} = \mathbf{0}$.

Then update the trial state variables

$$\Delta \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{n+1}^{\text{e,trial}} = \Delta \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{n+1}, \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{n+1}^{\text{p,trial}} = \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_n^p, \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{\text{eff},n+1}^{\text{p,trial}} = \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{\text{eff},n}^p, \boldsymbol{\sigma}_{n+1}^{\text{trial}} = \boldsymbol{C} : \Delta \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{n+1}^{\text{e,trial}} + \boldsymbol{\sigma}_n$$

c. Check the tension and compression status as well as the yield criterion

If $\sigma_{22,n+1}^{\text{trial}} + \sigma_{33,n+1}^{\text{trial}} > 0$, then the trial yield function is

$$F_{n+1}^{\text{trial}} = \sigma_{\text{eff},n+1}^{\text{trial}} - \left[R_{0T} + \sum_{i=1}^3 A_{iT} \cdot e^{-\frac{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{n+1}^{\text{p,trial}}}{B_{iT}}} \right]$$

Else, the trial yield function is

$$F_{n+1}^{\text{trial}} = \sigma_{\text{eff},n+1}^{\text{trial}} - \left[R_{0C} + \sum_{i=1}^3 A_{iC} \cdot e^{-\frac{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{n+1}^{\text{p,trial}}}{B_{iC}}} \right]$$

d. If $F_{n+1}^{\text{trial}} \leq 0$, no plastic deformation happens in the current increment and the state variables are

updated and then go to step 6.

$$\begin{aligned}\sigma_{n+1} &= \sigma_{n+1}^{\text{trail}}, \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{n+1} = \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_n + \Delta \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{n+1}, \\ \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{n+1}^e &= \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_n^e + \Delta \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{n+1}^{\text{e,trial}}, \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{n+1}^p = \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{n+1}^{\text{p,trial}}, \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{\text{eff},n+1}^p = \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{\text{eff},n+1}^{\text{p,trial}}\end{aligned}$$

e. If $F_{n+1}^{\text{trial}} > 0$, the plastic corrector is required:

1) Initialization of the Newton-Raphson iteration at $k=0$:

$$\Delta \lambda_{n+1}^{\text{p},0} = 0, \sigma_{n+1}^0 = \sigma_{n+1}^{\text{trial}}, \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{n+1}^{\text{p},0} = \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{n+1}^{\text{p,trial}}, \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{\text{eff},n+1}^{\text{p},0} = \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{\text{eff},n+1}^{\text{p,trial}}.$$

2) Calculate the increment of consistency parameter at $(k+1)$ th iteration:

$$\Delta \lambda_{n+1}^{\text{p},k+1} = \Delta \lambda_{n+1}^{\text{p},k} - \frac{F(\Delta \lambda_{n+1}^{\text{p},k})}{\partial F(\Delta \lambda_{n+1}^{\text{p},k}) / \partial \Delta \lambda_{n+1}^{\text{p},k}}$$

3) Update state variables

$$\begin{aligned}\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{n+1}^{\text{p},k+1} &= \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{n+1}^{\text{p},0} + \Delta \lambda_{n+1}^{\text{p},k+1} \cdot \frac{\partial F(\Delta \lambda_{n+1}^{\text{p},k})}{\partial \sigma_{n+1}^k}, \\ \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{\text{eff},n+1}^{\text{p},k+1} &= \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{\text{eff},n+1}^{\text{p},0} + \frac{2}{3} \sigma_{\text{eff},n+1}^k \cdot \Delta \lambda_{n+1}^{\text{p},k+1}, \\ \sigma_{n+1}^{k+1} &= \mathbf{C} : (\Delta \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{n+1} - \Delta \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{n+1}^{\text{p},k+1}) + \sigma_n.\end{aligned}$$

4) Check the yield criterion.

5) If $|F_{n+1}^{k+1}| > E$ where E denotes the converged tolerance and takes the value of 10^{-6} , then set $k = k + 1$ and go to Step e.2).

6) Else, $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{n+1}^{\text{p}} = \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{n+1}^{\text{p},k+1}$, $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{\text{eff},n+1}^{\text{p}} = \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{\text{eff},n+1}^{\text{p},k+1}$, $\sigma_{n+1} = \sigma_{n+1}^{k+1}$ and then go to Step f.

f. Calculate the consistent tangent stiffness tensor

1) If no yielding behavior occurs, then

$$\frac{d\sigma_{n+1}}{d\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{n+1}} = \mathbf{C}$$

2) Else, the consistent tangent stiffness is derived.

$$\frac{d\sigma_{n+1}}{d\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{n+1}} = \boldsymbol{\Xi}_{n+1} - \frac{(\boldsymbol{\Xi}_{n+1} : \partial_{\sigma} F_{n+1}) \otimes (\boldsymbol{\Xi}_{n+1} : \partial_{\sigma} g_{n+1})}{\partial_{\sigma} F_{n+1} : \boldsymbol{\Xi}_{n+1} : \partial_{\sigma} g_{n+1} - \frac{2}{3} \sigma_{\text{eff},n+1}^p \cdot \partial_{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{\text{eff}}^p} F_{n+1}}$$

$$\text{in which } \boldsymbol{\Xi}_{n+1} = (\mathbf{C}^{-1} + \Delta \lambda_{n+1}^{\text{p}} \partial_{\sigma\sigma}^2 g(\sigma_{n+1}))^{-1}.$$

3) Save the current internal state variables and then go to the next increment.

3 CASE STUDIES OF PREDICTING LAMINATE PLASTICITY

Based on above numerical implementation procedures, the developed elasto-plastic model is coded into user material subroutines and applied in FEA software ABAQUS to predict unidirectional laminates' elasto-plastic responses under off-axis tension and compression conditions. Three cases of off-axis loading tests in literatures [7, 13, 20] were simulated to validate the built 3D elasto-plastic constitutive model.

In case A, the off-axis tension and compression tests on HTS40/PA6 carbon/polyamide unidirectional laminates conducted by Wang, et al. [13] were simulated. Researched unidirectional laminates had the stack sequences of [15 °]₄₀, [45 °]₄₀ and [90 °]₄₀, which had the identical thickness of 3 mm. Gage length of specimens in tension was 100 mm and that in compression was 10 mm. The width for specimens in tension and compression was respectively 20 mm and 10 mm.

In both monotonic tension and compression tests, specimens were loaded at the constant strain rate of 1%/min. Because test results [13] contained the whole stress-strain history of laminates loaded up to failure and nonlinear plasticity prior to damage is the research focus, the stress-strain results before damage occurs were captured for determining model parameters. It was accomplished by assuming no damage occurs within the range of the stress level below which the initial slope of the reloading curves after unloading in cyclic tests kept unchanged. Namely, no degradation of laminate stiffness happening indicates no damage occurrence. Then, stress-strain data before damage could be derived based on the determined stress level. Figure 1 illustrates the effective stress-effective strain curves in tension tests and compression tests. Material parameters of HTS40/PA6 and relevant model parameters are given in Table 1. The values of transverse shear modulus G_{23} and poison ratio were not given by Refs [13, 25] and were respectively assumed to be 3.3 Gpa and 0.35, which later were proved to be acceptable based on the predicted laminate responses.

Figure 1: Effective stress-effective plastic strain curves of HTS40/PA6 laminates in (a) tension tests and (b) compression tests.

Material properties[25]	$E_1=113.1\text{Gpa}$, $E_2=E_3=10.3\text{Gpa}$, $G_{12}=G_{31}=3.8\text{Gpa}$, $G_{23}=3.3\text{Gpa}$ $\nu_{12}=\nu_{13}=0.42$, $\nu_{23}=0.35$
Fitted parameters	$a_{66}=1.27$, $a_{44}=2$, $a_{11}=0.05$, $\Gamma=1.03$, $R_{0T}=106.52$, $A_{1T}=-9.26$, $A_{2T}=-23.40$, $A_{3T}=-49.01$, $B_{1T}=1.03\text{E-}4$, $B_{2T}=6.06\text{E-}4$, $B_{3T}=0.0145$, $R_{0C}=145.37$, $A_{1C}=-48.62$, $A_{2C}=-47.15$, $A_{3C}=-49.38$, $B_{1C}=0.0141$, $B_{2C}=0.0153$, $B_{3C}=0.0145$.

Table 1: Material properties and model parameters for HTS40/PA6 in case A

In case B, the responses of unidirectional IM600/Q133 laminates within stacking sequences of $[\theta]_{12}$ subjected to uniaxial tension and compression loading [20] were studied. The fiber angle respective to loading axis took the value of 15° , 30° , 45° , 90° . Researched specimens exhibited on the width of 20 mm and the thickness of 1.8 mm. The gage length is 100 mm. The constant uniaxial loading speed is 1.0 mm/min. The effective stress-effective strain curves of IM600/Q133 laminates are shown in Figure 2. Parameters used in FEA tools are listed in Table 2.

Figure 2: Effective stress-effective plastic strain curves of IM600/Q133 laminates in (a) tension tests and (b) compression tests.

Material properties[24, 28]	$E_1=135.87\text{Gpa}, E_2=E_3=8.89\text{Gpa}, G_{12}=G_{31}=4.34\text{Gpa}, G_{23}=3.42\text{Gpa},$ $\nu_{12}=\nu_{13}=0.34, \nu_{23}=0.3$
Fitted parameters	$a_{66}=1.79, a_{44}=2, a_{11}=0.067, \Gamma=1.19, R_{0T}=168.47, A_{1T}=-21.27,$ $A_{2T}=-100.24, A_{3T}=-40.95, B_{1T}=1.89\text{E-}5, B_{2T}=2.35\text{E-}3, B_{3T}=2.38\text{E-}4,$ $R_{0C}=224.64, A_{1C}=-42.59, A_{2C}=-58.74, A_{3C}=-117.01,$ $B_{1C}=8.90\text{E-}5, B_{2C}=7.0\text{E-}4, B_{3C}=5.73\text{E-}3.$

Table 2. Material properties and model parameters for IM600/Q133 in case B

In case C, T800H/3633 carbon/epoxy laminates under off-axis tension and compression tests [7] were studied. $[\theta]_{20}$ and $[\theta]_{40}$ unidirectional laminates were respectively tested in tension and compression conditions. Tested specimens had the off-axis angles of 15°; 30°; 45°; 60°; 90°. Both tensile specimens and compressive specimens had the size of 120 mm length and 10 mm width. The thickness values of specimens in tension and compression are respectively 2.8 mm and 5.7 mm. The applied load speed was 0.5 mm/min in tension tests and 1 mm/min in compression tests. Figure 3 depicts the master curves of effective stress-effective strain in case C. Material parameters and fitted parameters can be found in Table 3. The values of transverse shear modulus G_{23} and poisson ratio were not given by Refs[7, 29] and were respectively assumed to be 4.9 Gpa and 0.31, which later were also proved to be acceptable based on the predicted laminate responses.

Figure 3: Effective stress-effective plastic strain curves of T800H/3633 laminates in (a) tension tests and (b) compression tests.

Material properties[7, 29]	$E_1=145\text{Gpa}$, $E_2=E_3=9.26\text{Gpa}$, $G_{12}=G_{31}=5.57\text{Gpa}$, $G_{23}=4.9\text{Gpa}$, $\nu_{12}=\nu_{13}=0.358$, $\nu_{23}=0.31$
Fitted parameters	$a_{66}=1.65$, $a_{44}=2$, $a_{11}=0.004$, $\Gamma=1.27$, $R_{0T}=233.49$, $A_{1T}=-74.18$, $A_{2T}=-41.78$, $A_{3T}=-117.52$, $B_{1T}=3.75\text{E-}5$, $B_{2T}=4.18\text{E-}4$, $B_{3T}=4.1\text{E-}3$, $R_{0C}=331.06$, $A_{1C}=-110.76$, $A_{2C}=-62.85$, $A_{3C}=-157.42$, $B_{1C}=4.39\text{E-}5$, $B_{2C}=6.68\text{E-}4$, $B_{3C}=7.16\text{E-}3$.

Table 3: Material properties and model parameters for T800H/3633 in case C

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

According to refs [7, 20], multiple specimens were tested for the same experimental configuration. Back-to-back strain gauges were also used in the tension and compression tests in ref [13]. In this research, the average values of the test results were adopted in this research for considering the scatter characteristics of experimental data.

Figure 4: Stress-strain curves of HTS40/PA6 laminates in (a) tension tests and (b) compression tests.

Figure 5: Stress-strain curves of IM600/Q133 laminates in (a) tension tests and (b) compression tests.

Figure 6: Stress-strain curves of T800H/3633 laminates in (a) tension tests and (b) compression tests.

Both predicted laminates' nonlinear responses and test results in three cases were illustrated in Figure 4 - Figure 6. Above figures demonstrated the good agreement between the simulation results and experimental results. Behaviors of laminate specimens under various off-axis loading angles in simulations catered well to experimentally observed responses, in which all of the simulated nonlinear stress-strain curves of specimens agreed well with corresponding experimental curves in all studied cases. When the angle between the loading axis and the orientation of reinforced fibers became larger, the matrix behaviors in laminates became more dominant and then the laminates exhibited softer. Moreover, the apparent differences between tension and compression responses of laminates were also precisely captured by the elasto-plastic constitutive model. Consequently, the newly-built elasto-plastic constitutive model was capable of reproducing laminates' nonlinear elasto-plastic behaviors in off-axis loading conditions.

According to Fig. 4- Fig. 6, the compression behaviors of laminates were stiffer than the tension behaviors of laminates in the same off-axis loading angle, which proved the tension and compression asymmetry of unidirectional (UD) laminates' responses in off-axis loading. The stiffer responses of UD laminates in compression could be attributed to the strengthening effects of negative transverse stress on laminates' mechanical behavior, which could be concluded from Eq (2). According to Table 1-3, the fitted values of Γ in three cases were all greater than one. As a result, the negative transverse stress in compressive condition could alleviate the effective stress defined in Eq (2) and prohibit the material from getting into the plastic deformation process, for which reason all researched laminates showed softer plastic deformation behaviors in tension conditions than that in compression scenarios.

Because the model parameters were mainly fitted from the effective stress- effective plastic strain curves, the accuracy of the elasto-plastic model in predicting laminates' off-axis loading responses mainly depends on the experimentally obtained stress-strain curves of laminates in loading conditions. In Figure 4 (b), simulated and experimental recorded compression results of laminates in the off-axis loading angles of 45 degrees and 90 degrees were nearly the same, which seem to be incorrect. It was caused by invalid test results of specimens which exhibited incorrect failure forms in off-axis loading tests [20]. In contrast, the valid distinctions were observed in compression results of laminates with off-axis loading angles of 45 degrees and 90 degrees in case B and case C and the constitutive model well reproduced this phenomenon.

5 CONCLUSIONS

In this study, a new elasto-plastic constitutive model describing unidirectional (UD) fiber reinforced polymer matrix composite (PMC) laminates' nonlinear deformation under off-axis tension and compression loading conditions is developed. The tension-compression asymmetry and the effect of the hydrostatic pressure term on plastic yielding are incorporated into the elasto-plastic model.

Following the non-associative flow rule, the new elasto-plastic constitutive model leads to a more simplified mathematical representations of incremental plastic strains than those based on models using the linear combination of plastic potential function and the hydrostatic pressure term [2-4].

The FEA of three cases of off-axis loading tests on unidirectional laminates made of different materials proved the capabilities of the model in predicting PMC laminates' nonlinear elasto-plastic responses. The differences between laminates' yielding behaviors under tension and compression were also well captured. The developed constitutive model is expected to support the analysis of laminate structures' nonlinear behaviors under complicated loading conditions.

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